

BladeBridge: Three Design Options for a Pedestrian Bridge made from Decommissioned 53 Meter Wind Turbine Blades

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ABSTRACT

In recent decades, the widespread use of wind power has led to the rise of a new environmental issue in the form of wind turbine blade waste. To combat the landfilling and incineration of what is projected to be millions of tons GFRP blades, the Re-Wind Network aims to find solutions to repurpose wind blades in structural applications. This paper reports on the design and analysis of three options for an 18.5 meter pedestrian bridge made using decommissioned 53-meter blades. Maximum strains and deflections found through structural analysis of these BladeBridges are used to assess the feasibility of each option.

KEYWORDS

Composite material waste; wind turbine blades; repurposing; pedestrian bridges

INTRODUCTION

Over the last few decades, wind energy has become an essential source of power around the world, allowing many countries to divest from traditional nonrenewable energy sources. However, a new environmental issue is beginning to arise in the form of wind turbine blade waste. Wind turbine blades are made of glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) composite materials and are designed for a service life of 20-25 years, after which they are then considered to be at their end of life (EOL) and are required to be decommissioned regardless of their condition. Many more blades are also decommissioned prematurely due to repowering, a process in which wind farms are incentivized by the government to upgrade the rotors and turbines with newer, larger, and more efficient systems to produce more power. Waste management for GFRP is difficult, as the material is not biodegradable and is difficult and energy intensive to recycle (Cooperman et al. 2021). The scale of EOL blade waste makes it an especially concerning issue — with typical blade lengths ranging from 40 to 60 meters, the volume and mass of blade waste will increase dramatically as wind energy producers decommission and repower wind farms in the coming few years.

The ReWind Network was established in 2017 to address the growing issue of wind turbine blade waste. The network consists of researchers and industry professionals in the US, UK, and Ireland and focuses on repurposing FRP wind turbine blades in structural applications. In the last few years, the differences between repurposing, reusing, recycling and disposal have been discussed in numerous publications (Nagle et al., 2020, Gentry et al., 2020). The network has created a “Design Catalogue” which showcases concepts of various potential repurposing solutions (McDonald et al., 2022). Of these solutions, Re-Wind has been primarily focusing on two applications: an electrical transmission structures (BladePole) and a pedestrian bridge (BladeBridge). In 2021, Re-Wind installed its first public blade repurposing structure: a BladeBridge on a greenway in County Cork, Ireland (Ruane et al., 2022). Since then, there has been a second BladeBridge constructed on a test site by Queens University Belfast (QUB) in Northern Ireland, UK (Suhail, 2019). A BladePole demonstration is planned for construction in South Carolina, USA in 2024 (Henao et al, 2022).

This paper focuses on Re-Wind’s third BladeBridge project: a public installation of two wind blade pedestrian bridges in collaboration with the City of Atlanta. The bridges will be installed in Beaverbrook Park, a 6.8 acre park located in Atlanta’s Wildwood neighborhood, as part of a larger project to expand the park’s walking trail into an adjacent forested area. The trail will cross an existing creek at two locations, and requires a bridge span of at least 18 meters at both locations to properly account for flood levels and to avoid critical tree root zones. The Re-Wind team worked with

an original equipment manufacturer (OEM) partner to procure six, 53-meter decommissioned wind blades for use on this project. A 3D digital model of the blade as well as the composite layup were provided to the Georgia Tech Re-Wind team by the OEM.

Using wind turbine blades in pedestrian bridges presents several challenges. The loads that the blades will experience in this application differ from those that were considered in the blades' original design. The unique geometry of the blades requires the use of complex modelling techniques to extract the necessary engineering properties. In addition, the fact that these blades are at their first end of life adds the challenge of characterizing their remaining structural capability, perhaps requiring higher safety factors to ensure that they can be safely used in a public structure. However, while wind blade pedestrian bridges appear to be a novel concept, there are substantial precedents for the use of FRP as a pedestrian bridge building material. A prominent example in the United States is E.T. Techtonics (owned and operated by Creative Composites Group), a firm which specializes in the design and construction of pultruded FRP truss bridges (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Pultruded fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) pedestrian bridge designed and produced by E.T. Techtonics.

There are several benefits in using FRP rather than traditional materials such as timber and steel — FRP is a lighter and longer lasting material, which allows for lower transportation and maintenance costs. In addition, FRP is weather and corrosion resistant and will not leach any harmful substances into its surroundings (Creative Composites Group, n.d.). Other similar FRP pedestrian bridge suppliers in the United States include Bridge Brothers in Atlanta (Bridge Brothers, n.d.) and Bedford Reinforced Plastics in Pennsylvania (Bedford Plastics, n.d.); there are also many similar firms around the world, such as Module Systems & Solutions in Norway (Module Systems & Solutions, n.d.) and Fibercore Europe in the Netherlands (Fibercore Europe, n.d.).

WIND BLADE PROPERTIES

A typical wind blade cross section is presented in Figure 2. The airfoil-shaped beam structure is oriented in so-called edgewise bending, with the trailing edge (TE) of the blade oriented up, which is the configuration used on most of the Re-Wind Network bridge concepts. The leading edge (LE) is depicted at the bottom of the airfoil. The right side of the airfoil, or the convex side, is known as the high pressure (HP) surface, and the left or concave side is the low pressure (LP) surface. Near the center of both the HP and LP sides, there is a region of thicker FRP material known as the spar cap, which serves as the primary structural portion of the wind blade and stiffens the blade in flapwise bending. The airfoil is held together and stiffened by a single shear web typically located in the spar cap region. In addition to FRP composite laminates, additional materials include a thin outer protective coating (gelcoat) and lightweight foam/balsa materials in the shell. For the purposes of analysis and testing, only the blade's FRP material is considered to contribute to its structural capability.

Due to the longitudinal stiffness changes in laminate around the perimeter of the airfoil, with some laminates dominated by unidirectional (UD) fiber, and others with mostly bi-axial (0/90 and ± 45 degree plies), flexural stresses differ at various regions when the blade is subjected to edgewise

bending, as shown in Figure 2. Stresses are highest in the regions with stiffer FRP material — mainly in the spar cap, but also portions of the leading and trailing edges. This stiffer material primarily consists of many layers of unidirectional (UD) fibers oriented longitudinally (parallel to the length of the blade). The longitudinal modulus of the spar cap material is assumed in this paper to be 36.8 GPa, which was found through prior testing conducted on similar blades (Alshannaq et al., 2022). The modulus of the remaining regions in the airfoil is taken as 10 GPa per analysis completed by Ruane et al., (2022).

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of flexural stress and strain along an airfoil section under edgewise bending. Flexural stress is larger in the trailing edge, spar cap, and leading edge, where there is a higher concentration of unidirectional (UD) fibers.

Figure 3 shows an elevation view of the 53-meter blade used for the BladeBridges, along with the corresponding flexural and torsional stiffnesses associated with each station, measured as distance from the root end of the blade. It can be seen that airfoil dimensions, and thus material and engineering properties, vary drastically depending on the station number. BladeBridge options 1 and 2, discussed below, will use an 18.5 meter blade section from stations 22.5 m to 41 m, while option 3 requires a larger section from stations 12 m to 30.5 m. These sections were chosen based on strength, stiffness as well as on geometric considerations as the blades also serve as the pedestrian bridge guardrails.

Figure 3: Elevation view of a 53-meter wind turbine blade and corresponding flexural and torsional stiffness along the length of the blade.

PEDESTRIAN BRIDGE DESIGN REQUIREMENTS

Being installed in a City of Atlanta public park, the two bridges must satisfy the Georgia Department of Transportation (GDOT) Bridge and Structures Policy Manual (GDOT, 2023). The manual states that all pedestrian overpass structures should be designed in accordance with the AASHTO LRFD Guide Specifications for the Design of Pedestrian Bridges (AASHTO, 2009), and thus the AASHTO specifications were the primary source used for the BladeBridge design requirements.

The AASHTO specifications require pedestrian bridges to be designed for a uniform pedestrian loading of 90 psf (4.3 kN/m²) patterned to produce maximum load effects. Additional loading is required if vehicular access is granted, however, these bridges are designed with a 6 foot (1.8 m) deck width and will prohibit vehicular access. For the purposes of this study, wind loads and fatigue loads were not considered in the analysis. Deflection requirements state that the deflection of the bridge due to unfactored pedestrian loading should not exceed 1/360 of the span length. Checks for vibrations due to walking excitation and calculation of the natural frequency (AISC, 2003) will be considered in the final design but are not covered in this paper.

The AASHTO specifications were also compared to the Eurocode (Eurocode, 2003), which was the basis used for the design of the previous two BladeBridges. The loading requirements are slightly higher in the Eurocode, with a uniformly distributed live load, q_{fk} , of 5 kN/m². Similar to AASHTO, it is not required to consider vehicle loading if access is permanently prevented. Deflection limits are not stated, and vibration requirements are similar to those stated in AASHTO.

In terms of safety requirements, the AASHTO LRFD Bridge Design Specifications (AASHTO, 2020) requires a guardrail height no less than 42 inches (1.07 m). The Eurocode is again slightly more conservative, requiring a parapet height of 1.4 m.

BRIDGE DESIGN OPTIONS

Three options were considered for the design of the two BladeBridges, as shown in Figure 4. All three options use the wind blades as the primary longitudinal girders and use the 18.5 m blade section as discussed previously. The first option (Figure 4a) is known as the “two blade simply supported” bridge, which consists of two blade girders on either side of the deck and foundations on each side of the span. This is the most “conventional” design option, as it closely mimics the previous two BladeBridges (Ruane, 2022, Suhail, 2019). Some concerns were raised regarding constructability of this option, as the park site is heavily forested with several protected trees, and budget restrictions limit the machinery available for construction. Thus, it might not be feasible to move equipment and materials across the creek to install foundations on both sides of the bridge.

As a result, the second option (Figure 4b) was created, known as the “two blade cantilevered” bridge. Similar to the first option, this bridge uses two blades as the longitudinal girders, but in this case both of the foundations are on one side of the bridge. This allows for easier construction access, however it calls for a more complex foundation design and will result in higher deflections at the free end. The final option (Figure 4c), the “single blade torsional” bridge, aimed to explore a design using only one blade. The single blade is supported by foundations similar to the first option, with the deck supported off to one side of the blade and a traditional guardrail lining the open end of the deck. The asymmetrical nature of this design is appealing, however that same attribute means that the analysis and design of this option is more complex than the previous two, and the construction would be more cost-intensive.

The wind blades are intended to also serve as the guardrails for the bridges, and thus the height measured from the deck to the trailing edge will be lower than the minimum guardrail height at the smaller ends of the blades. However, the International Building Code (ICC, 2021) states that the use of guardrails at a height of 42 inches is only required for ramps located more than 30 inches (0.76 m) above the grade below at any point within 36 inches (0.91 m) horizontally to the edge of the ramp. As shown in Figure 4, the ends of the bridge will extend beyond the creek, which means that the elevation change will be below the value that requires a full height guardrail.

Figure 4. Three design options for the Bladebridge. All options use the blades as the primary longitudinal girders.

SIMPLIFIED STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Support Conditions and Loading

The bridge concepts introduced previously are designed with varying support conditions. Both the simply supported and cantilevered bridge concepts assume pinned connections at one end and a roller connection at the other. While the foundations for these bridges will likely contain some fixity, it is conservative to assume pinned-roller support conditions. The one blade torsional bridge concept is similar; however, the support conditions include torsional fixity at both ends of each wind blade. Live pedestrian loading for the bridge is a 90 psf (439 kg/m²) load distributed to the deck according to pedestrian bridge design standards (AASHTO, 2009). This live load is a conservative and codified load that is likely much higher than the traffic the bridge will expect to service. The dead load for the two blade simply supported bridge concept and the two blade cantilever bridge concept is 40 psf (195 kg/m²). The dead load for the one blade torsional bridge concept is 30 psf (146 kg/m²). This dead load estimate considers the weight of the wind turbine blades and of 50-millimeter-thick wooden decking on the bridge. This dead load is conservatively simplified to be distributed uniformly to the deck, although it likely follows a trapezoidal loading pattern that is more heavily weighted at end of the bridge with the larger sections of the wind blade.

Structural Analysis

The three BladeBridge concepts are analysed via a custom-built spreadsheet that accounts for the varying geometric and material properties of the wind turbine blade depending on the section of the blade. The blade is divided into 0.5-meter sections, with effective modulus of elasticity, E_i ; modulus of elasticity, I_i ; effective shear modulus, G_i ; and torsional moment of inertia, J_i of each section, i , provided by the OEM. Additional section properties were extracted from the geometric model to allow for the calculation of flexural stresses in the spar cap and in those regions containing unidirectional plies. To calculate the strains and stresses experienced by the blade, first the curvature, k_i , along each section is calculated where M_i is the moment applied at that section of the blade (Eq. 1).

$$k_i = \frac{M_i}{E_i I_i} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Using curvature, the strain, ϵ_{ij} , along each section and part of the blade can be found by multiplying the curvature with the neutral axis depths, c_j , for the edges and spar caps of the blade (Eq. 2).

$$\epsilon_{ij} = k_i \cdot c_j \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Given the strain, the stress, σ_{ij} , for each section and part of the blade can be found by multiplying the strain with the modulus of elasticity, E_j , of the edges and spar caps of the blade (Eq. 3).

$$\sigma_{ij} = \epsilon_{ij} \cdot E_j \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

To calculate the deflection along the the blade, the curvature as a function of the length along the girder, z , is numerically integrated twice using a left Riemann sum at 0.5 meter intervals, corresponding to each section of the blade (Eq. 4). C is the constant of integration due to the support conditions.

$$\delta = \sum_{i=1}^n \{ (\sum_{i=1}^n k_i \cdot 0.5m + C) \cdot 0.5m \} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

The max torsional stress, τ_i , at each section of the girder for the torsional bridge concept is calculated using Eq. 5 where T_i is the applied torque and r_i is the distance on the edge of the blade farthest from the centroid of the wind blade for each section of the blade.

$$\tau_i = \frac{T_i r_i}{J_i} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

The max torsional strain, γ_i , at each section of the girder for the torsional bridge concept is calculated using Eq. 6 where T_i is the applied torque and r_i is the distance on the edge of the blade farthest from the centroid of the wind blade for each section of the blade.

$$\gamma_i = \frac{T_i r_i}{J_i G_i} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

The angle of twist, θ , along the wind blade for the torsional bridge concept is calculated similarly to deflection of the girder. A left Riemann sum is taken of the applied torque, T_i , over the shear modulus for each section of the blade to find the angle of twist along the length of the girder (Eq. 7).

$$\theta = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{T_i \cdot 0.5m}{G_i} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

For the two girder simply supported bridge concept, the loading on the bridge is distributed evenly to both blades of the bridge, and the ensuing moment curve for a simply supported beam given the loading is determined. Using the structural analysis spreadsheet outlined earlier, the strain, stress, and deflection of the girder along the length of the bridge is found, as visible in Figure 5. For strain and stress, tension is positive, and compression is negative.

Figure 5: Analysis diagrams for two blade simply supported design option.

For the two girder cantilever bridge concept, the loading of the bridge is equally distributed to both blades of the bridge. The strain, stress, and deflection of the girder along the length of the bridge can be found in Figure 6. For strain and stress, tension is positive, and compression is negative. As visible, this bridge concept experiences a large amount of deflection at the unsupported end of the bridge.

c) Deflection (mm) along single girder
 Figure 6: Analysis diagrams for two blade cantilever design option.

For the single girder torsional bridge concept, the loading on the bridge deck creates a torsional force on the blade. The wind turbine blade is fixed against this torsion on both ends of the blade, leading to an uneven distribution of the torque resisted by the foundations due to the unique geometry of the wind turbine blade. The flexural strains, stresses, and deflection on the wind blade can be seen in Figure 7. Figure 7 additionally contains the angle of rotation of the wind blade and the strains and shear stresses along its length due to the torsional loading of the blade. These strains and stresses are maximized in the trailing edge as this location is the farthest distance from the centroid of the blade. Simplifying the cross section of the wind blade to a rectangle, the shear stress due to bending, τ_b , at the neutral axis can be approximated. In Eq. 8, V , the value for the shear force at the thin end of the simply supported torsional girder and A , the cross-sectional area of the blade section are used to calculate the shear stress. This is the location with the largest bending shear stress, and it is only a small fraction of the torsional shear stress. Given that this bending shear stress tapers off to 0 approaching the trailing edge, the torsional shear stress governs and is the only shear stress shown.

$$\tau_b = \frac{3V}{2A} = \frac{3 \cdot 96090}{2 \cdot 0.115m^2} = 1.25 \text{ MPa} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

a) Flexural strain (microstrain) of uniaxial FRP along single girder.

b) Flexural stress (MPa) of uniaxial FRP along single girder.

Figure 7: Analysis diagrams for one blade torsional design option.

Table 1 displays the maximum strains, stresses, and deflections in the girders present in each of the three bridge design options under full unfactored live and dead loading.

Table 1: Maximum strains, stresses, and deflections for bridge concepts.

Bridge Concept	Max Flexural Strain (microstrain)	Max Flexural Stress (MPa)	Max Deflection (mm)	Max Shear Strain (microstrain)	Max Shear Stress (MPa)
Simply Supported	1400	51.6	47.3	-	-
Cantilever	-1010	-37.0	92.5	-	-
Torsional	804	29.6	18.0	-6570	-21.0

Trailing Edge Buckling

A common failure mode in edgewise bending of wind blades is buckling at the trailing edge. A preliminary analysis was performed to ensure that the maximum flexural stresses experienced at the trailing edge of the BladeBridge girders are below that of the critical buckling stress. For the purposes of this check, the trailing edge was idealized as an orthotropic plate under uniform axial compression. Material properties were obtained from prior Re-Wind studies (Alshannaq et al., 2022), and trailing edge dimensions were obtained from a 3D model provided by the wind blade OEM (Table 2).

Table 2. Summary of values used for trailing edge buckling calculations.

Material Properties	
Longitudinal modulus (E_{11})	36.8 GPa
Transverse modulus (E_{22})	10.7 GPa
Shear modulus (G_{12})	4.57 GPa
In-plane poisson's ratio (ν_{12})	0.25
Dimensions	
Trailing edge minimum thickness (t)	21.94 mm
Trailing edge width (b)	390 mm

The following equation for critical buckling stress (Eq. 9) was obtained from the Structural Plastics Design Manual (ASCE, 1984). This equation assumes one free edge and one fixed edge on an orthotropic plate. In the case of the trailing edge, the “tip” of the trailing edge is considered the free edge, and the bottom of the trailing edge that connects to the rest of the airfoil is the fixed edge. A diagram depicting the assumed support conditions for this equation is shown in Figure 8. Minimum values for thickness t and width b are used, and these values are assumed to be uniform along the length of the plate. Flexural stiffness coefficients D_{11} , D_{12} and D'_{12} are calculated using the material properties listed in Table 2.

$$\sigma_{xc} = \frac{\pi^2}{b^2 t} (0.935 \sqrt{D_{11} D_{12}} - 0.656 D_{12} + 2.082 D'_{12}) \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

Figure 8. Assumed idealization of the trailing edge as an orthotropic plate. (ASCE, 1984).

The critical buckling stress for the trailing edge was calculated to be 54.38 MPa. As listed in the previous section, the maximum flexural stress experienced in the trailing edge is 30.0 MPa in the two blade simply supported option. Thus, it was determined that trailing edge buckling will not be a risk under the assumed loads for the BladeBridges.

DISCUSSION

Although flexural capacity is typically assessed in civil/structural engineering in terms of calculated stresses in relation to material strengths, composite material engineers dealing with complex multidirectional laminates often use strain limits for early-stage structural assessment and design. The proposed limit for these initial feasibility assessments is 3000 microstrain for longitudinal stresses under unfactored service loads. The maximum flexural strain experienced in the blades for all three design options is 1400 microstrain in the two blade simply supported option. This is less than half of the ultimate strain, which shows that the wind blades have more than enough flexural strength to support the given loads regardless of the design option.

With all three options able to support the required pedestrian loading, the deciding factors for the selection of the appropriate option were deflection, shear capacity, and constructability. The cantilever bridge concept was ruled out due to the fact that it has a maximum deflection of over 90 mm at the unsupported end, which is higher than the maximum deflection stated in the code of 1/360 of the span length (51 mm). The torsional bridge concept shows potential for future use, as well as high architectural appeal; however, it was determined that more research on the torsional strength of these wind turbine blades and fixed torsional foundations is needed prior to designing a bridge for public use. The initial proposed strain limit for the blades under shear stresses is 1000 microstrain, and the current design exceeds this limit several times over with a maximum shear strain of 6570 microstrain. In addition, given the site and budget constraints, it was determined that it will not be feasible to

construct the single blade bridge this project. As a result, the two blade simply supported bridge was chosen as the best option for both BladeBridges.

It should be noted that more analysis is needed prior to construction of these bridges. Vibrations will need to be considered to ensure serviceability. While the natural frequency of a bridge is tied to vertical deflection, the fact that FRP is lightweight makes conducting this analysis important despite the acceptable deflection of the bridge. A more complex finite element analysis is also important to validate results found via traditional structural analysis methods, and to confirm the preliminary calculations that trailing edge buckling will not be a risk under service loads.

Figure 9 displays in more detail the two blade simply supported bridge concept. The deck structure consists of a 5mm deck sitting above a series of transverse beams. These transverse beams are attached to an edge beam on each blade using stainless steel joist hangers (Figure 10a). These edge beams are then connected to the blade using custom designed connections known as “universal connectors” (Figure 10b), which fit the curvature of the blade and are attached via blind bolts. The foundations for each end of the bridge will consist of a precast concrete form that the blades can fit into. This precast section will be connected via epoxied dowels to a larger concrete foundation that will be poured on site and connect to a series of installed helical piles. Before constructing the two bridges for installation at Beaverbrook Park, a prototype will first be built and tested to failure at the Georgia Tech Structural Engineering and Materials Laboratory. This prototype will not include the helical pile foundations, as the bridge will be built on an existing concrete slab (Figure 9). Once the prototype bridge is completed and the design is validated through load testing, the final two bridges will then be constructed.

Figure 9: 3D model of BladeBridge prototype for installation at the Georgia Tech Structural Engineering and Materials Laboratory.

a) Joist hanger.

b) Universal connector.

Figure 10. Steel connection designs for the BladeBridge.

CONCLUSION

Through the implementation of recycled wind turbine blades in pedestrian bridge construction, we can address the growing issue of blade waste and contribute to a more sustainable future for renewable energy infrastructure while creating architecturally appealing, long lasting bridge infrastructure. This current BladeBridge project builds upon the Re-Wind Network's prior body of work and aims to promote further exploration and adoption of repurposed wind blades in structural applications in the United States.

CITATIONS

- Alshannaq, A. A., Bank, L. C., Scott, D. W., & Gentry, T. R. (2021). Structural Analysis of a Wind Turbine Blade Repurposed as an Electrical Transmission Pole. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 25(4), 04021023. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CC.1943-5614.0001136](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0001136)
- Alshannaq, A. A., Respert, J. A., Bank, L. C., Scott, D. W., & Gentry, T. R. (2022). As-Received Physical and Mechanical Properties of the Spar Cap of a GE37 Decommissioned GFRP Wind Turbine Blade. *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, 34(10), 04022266. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)MT.1943-5533.0004410](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)MT.1943-5533.0004410)
- American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO). (2009). *LRFD Guide Specifications for the Design of Pedestrian Bridges* (2nd edition).
- American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO). (2020). *LRFD Bridge Design Specifications* (9th edition).
- American Institute of Steel Construction (AISC). (2003). *Design Guide 11: Floor Vibrations Due to Human Activity* (1st edition).
- American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE). (1984). *Structural Plastics Design Manual*.
- Bedford Reinforced Plastics. (n.d.). ReadySpan Pedestrian Bridges. <https://bedfordreinforced.com/products/readyspan/>
- Bridge Brothers. (n.d.). Pedestrian Bridges. <https://bridgebrothers.com/pedestrian-bridges/>
- Cooperman, A., Eberle, A., Lantz, E. (2022), Wind Turbine Blade Material in the United States: Quantities, Costs, and End-of-Life Options, Resources, Conservation and Recycling, Volume 168, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105439>.
- Creative Composites Group. (n.d.). Fiberglass Pedestrian Bridges. <https://www.creativecompositesgroup.com/products/pedestrian-bridges-boardwalks/pedestrian-bridges>
- EN 1991-2 (2003) (English): Eurocode 1: Actions on structures - Part 2: Traffic loads on bridges [Authority: The European Union Per Regulation 305/2011, Directive 98/34/EC, Directive 2004/18/EC]
- Fircore Europe. (n.d.). Composite Bridges for Cyclists and Pedestrians. <https://www.fircore-europe.com/en/products/bicycle-and-pedestrian-bridges/>
- Gentry, T. R., Al-Haddad, T., Bank, L. C., Arias, F. R., Nagle, A., & Leahy, P. (2020). Structural Analysis of a Roof Extracted from a Wind Turbine Blade. *Journal of Architectural Engineering*, 26(4), 04020040. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)AE.1943-5568.0000440](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)AE.1943-5568.0000440)
- Henao, Y., Nagle, A., Gentry, T. R., Bank, L. C., & Al-Haddad, T. (2022) "Comparative Lifecycle Analysis between Wind Turbine Blades Repurposed as Energy Transmission Poles and Conventional Steel Poles. NOCMAT 2022: The International Conference on Non-conventional Materials and Technologies 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6998159>
- International Code Council (ICC). (2021). *International Building Code*.
- McDonald, A., Bank, L.C., Kiemicki, C., Bermek, M.S., Zhang, Z., Poff, A., Kakkad, S., Lau, E., Suhail, R., & Gentry, T.R. (2022). Re-Wind Design Catalog 2nd Edition Fall/Autumn 2022. <https://www.re-wind.info/>
- Module Solutions & Systems (n.d.). FRP Bicycle and Pedestrian Bridges. <https://modulesolutions.no/onshore/products-solutions/frp-bicycle-and-pedestrian-bridges/>
- Nagle, A., Bank, L., Delaney, E., & Leahy, P. (2020). A Comparative Life Cycle Assessment Between Landfilling And Co-Processing Of Waste From Decommissioned Irish Wind Turbine Blades. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123321>
- Ruane, K., Zhang, Z., Nagle, A., Huynh, A., Alshannaq, A., McDonald, A., Leahy, P., Soutsos, M., McKinley, J., Gentry, T. R., & Bank, L. (2022). Material and Structural Characterization of a Wind Turbine Blade for Use as a Bridge Girder. *Transportation Research Record*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03611981221083619>
- Suhail, R., Chen, J., Gentry, T. R., Tasistro-Hart, B., Xue, Y., & Bank, L. C. 2019. Analysis and Design of a Pedestrian Bridge with Decommissioned FRP Windblades and Concrete. *Proceedings of FRPRCS14*, Belfast, UK, June 4-7, 2019, paper no. 176.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is proprietary and owned by the OEM.